

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of Mannich bases of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide derived from sulphonamides

Sheela Joshi*, Anju Das Manikpuri and Deepak Khare

School of Chemical Science, Devi Ahilya University, Indore-452 001, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : spjoshil1@rediffmail.com; anjudas792000@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-731-470372

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Abstract : The Mannich derivatives of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide with formaldehyde and various sulphonamides were synthesized for study of their biological effects. The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses, UV, IR and ^1H NMR spectral studies. The biological screening of these synthesized compounds were done against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* (Gram-positive bacteria) with a view to explore their antimicrobial action by disk diffusion method at 40, 80 and 160 mg/ml respectively. The results reveal the potential and importance of mounting new Mannich bases against pathogens under investigation and found to be low toxic as ascertained by LD_{50} test.

Keywords : 2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzamide, sulphonamides, Mannich reaction, Mannich bases, antimicrobial activity, statistical analysis.

Introduction

The aminoalkylation of aromatic substrates by the Mannich reaction is of considerable importance for the synthesis and modification of biologically active compounds^{1,2}. It also provides a convenient access to many useful synthetic building blocks because the amino group can be easily converted into a variety of other functionalities³⁻⁵.

2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzamide is the derivative of substituted benzoic acid⁶ that possesses a therapeutic use (veterinary), as coccidiostat. It is used versus infections caused by protozoa and bacteria especially in the treatment of coccidiosis caused by *E. tenella*, *E. necatrix* and *E. acervulina*. Moreover, sulphonamides are building block of several types of drugs⁷⁻⁹. Hence, it was considered of attention to determine whether the compounds resulting from the aminomethylation of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide moiety would possess significant biological potency at various concentrations. In continuation of our work on antimicrobial activity of Mannich bases^{10,11}, herein we describe the Mannich bases of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide, keeping this in view that they are found to be more potent, less toxic and claimed to have a wide spectrum of biological activities than their parent compound. From the above view and our present study, the present paper reports the antimicrobial evaluation of Mannich bases 3a-3d.

Results and discussion

The structure of the synthesized Mannich bases was elucidated by elementary analyses, UV, IR and ^1H NMR findings. All spectral data were in accordance with the assumed structure. The spectral data of novel compounds (3a-3d) are summarized in Table 2.

All the synthesized Mannich bases were tested for their antimicrobial activity using the disk diffusion method¹² by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against some gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria such as *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. The diameter of zone of inhibition was measured in mm. The antimicrobial screening data were recorded in Tables 3 and 4.

Antibacterial screening of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide methylamines against *B. subtilis* show significant results. All the Mannich bases show antimicrobial activity against this bacterium except 3a. Table 3 reflects that the compound 3d is statistically superior to other Mannich bases in checking the growth of *B. subtilis*. In case of *S. aureus* all Mannich bases show antimicrobial activity against this bacterium except 3c. Table 3 further reflects that compound 3d is statistically superior to all arbitrarily chosen concentrations in checking the growth of *S. aureus*.

The concentration of 160 mg mL⁻¹ is found significantly superior to concentrations 80 mg mL⁻¹ and 40 mg

Table 1. Characterization data of Mannich bases of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide with sulphonamides

Sl. no.	Compd.	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :		
				Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
3a	2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzamido-methyl- <i>N'</i> -2-pyrimidinyl- <i>p</i> -aminobenzene sulfonamide	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₅ SCl	160–165	46.59 (46.70)	3.81 (3.24)	17.92 (18.16)
3b	2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzamido-methyl- <i>N'</i> -[5-methyl-4-isoxazolyl- <i>p</i> -aminobenzene] sulfonamide	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₆ SCl	120	46.25 (46.40)	3.74 (3.43)	15.74 (15.03)
3c	2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzamido-methyl- <i>p</i> -aminobenzene sulfonamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₅ SCl	110	43.24 (43.02)	3.51 (3.33)	14.07 (14.34)
3d	2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzamido-methyl- <i>p</i> -aminobenzene sulphonyl acetamide	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₆ SCl	115	45.20 (45.01)	3.58 (3.51)	13.28 (13.13)

Table 2. Spectral data of Mannich bases of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide with sulphonamides

Compd.	UV (λ _{max} , nm)	IR (ν, cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ values in ppm)
3a	208 (secondary amine), 212 (chloro group in the molecule), 210 (amido moiety), 225 (sulphoxide group in the molecule), 240 (benzene nucleus containing nitro group), 265 (sulphonamide moiety)	3400 (s, asymmetric stretching of NH bonds in secondary amides), 2900 (s, asymmetric stretching of C–H bonds in CH ₂), 2850 (w, symmetric stretching of C–H bonds in CH ₂), 1750 (s, stretching vibrations of carbonyl group of nitrogen containing heterocyclic ring), 1480 (s, CH ₂ scissoring vibrations)	2.60 (d, CH ₂), 6.25 (s, NH of sulphonamide), 8.42 (t, CONH), 7.86 (various ring proton), 10.60 (s, SO ₂ NH)
3b	206 (secondary amine), 214 (chloro group in the molecule), 210 (amido moiety), 225 (sulphoxide group in the molecule), 240 (benzene nucleus containing nitro group), 260 (sulphonamide moiety)	3200 (s, asymmetric stretching of NH bonds in secondary amides), 2800 (s, asymmetric stretching of C–H bonds in CH ₂), 2750 (w, symmetric stretching of C–H bonds in CH ₂), 1650 (s, stretching vibrations of carbonyl group of nitrogen containing heterocyclic ring), 1380 (s, CH ₂ scissoring vibrations)	2.50 (d, CH ₂), 6.20 (s, NH of sulphonamide), 8.32 (t, CONH), 7.83 (various ring proton), 10.60 (s, SO ₂ NH)
3c	202 (secondary amine), 208 (chloro group in the molecule), 210 (amido moiety), 226 (sulphoxide	3300 (s, asymmetric stretching of NH bonds in secondary amides), 2950 (s, asymmetric stretching of C–H bonds in CH ₂), 2750 (w, symmetric	2.55 (d, CH ₂), 6.24 (s, NH of sulphonamide), 8.40 (t, CONH), 7.85 (various ring proton), 10.20 (s, SO ₂ NH)

	group in the molecule), 240 (benzene nucleus containing nitro group), 264 (sulphonamide moiety)	stretching of C-H bonds in CH ₂), 1700 (s, stretching vibrations of carbonyl group of nitrogen containing heterocyclic ring), 1400 (s, CH ₂ scissoring vibrations)	
3d	206 (secondary amine), 208 (chloro group in the molecule), 210 (amido moiety), 223 (sulphoxide group in the molecule), 242 (benzene nucleus containing nitro group), 262 (sulphonamide moiety)	3400 (s, asymmetric stretching of NH bonds in secondary amides), 2800 (s, asymmetric stretching of C-H bonds in CH ₂), 2750 (w, symmetric stretching of C-H bonds in CH ₂), 1650 (s, stretching vibrations of carbonyl group of nitrogen containing heterocyclic ring), 1300 (s, CH ₂ scissoring vibrations)	2.52 (d, CH ₂), 6.22 (s, NH of sulphonamide), 8.38 (t, CONH), 7.88 (various ring proton), 10.40 (s, SO ₂ NH)

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamidomethyl amines against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*

Compd.	(Zone of inhibition in mm)							
	<i>B. subtilis</i> (concn. in mg/ml)				<i>S. aureus</i> (concn. in mg/ml)			
	40	80	160	Average	40	80	160	Average
3a	-	-	-	-	7.0	7.5	7.5	7.33
3b	7.0	7.5	8.5	7.67	7.5	7.5	8.0	7.67
3c	7.5	8.0	8.5	8.0	-	-	-	-
3d	13.5	18.5	21.5	17.83	12.5	17.5	21.5	17.17
Avg. of concn.	7.00	8.5	9.62		6.75	8.12	9.25	
	S.Ed.	CD at 5%			S.Ed.	CD at 5%		
Compound	0.329	0.718			0.528	1.150		
Concentration	0.120	0.246			0.147	0.302		
Interaction	0.318	0.652			0.389	0.798		

S.Ed.-Standard error of difference; CD-Critical difference.

mL⁻¹ in checking the growth of both microorganisms.

The antimicrobial activity of Mannich bases was compared with their corresponding sulphonamides (Table 4). It will be interesting to compare changes in the antimicrobial activity of Mannich bases with the changes in their structure. In all cases, a change in structure occurred with the substitution of hydrogen(s) of the -NH₂ group attached at SO₂ position. These groups were :

The results indicate that for compounds 3d are significantly superior to their corresponding sulphonamide

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamidomethyl amines against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*

Compd.	(Zone of inhibition in mm)							
	<i>B. subtilis</i> (concn. in mg/ml)				<i>S. aureus</i> (concn. in mg/ml)			
	40	80	160	Average	40	80	160	Average
Average								
3a	-	-	-	-	7.0	7.5	7.5	7.33
Sulphadiazine	-	-	-	-	7.0	7.5	9.5	8.0
3b	7.0	7.5	8.5	7.67	7.5	7.5	8.0	7.67
Sulphamethoxazole	15.5	18.5	20.0	18.0	19.5	20.5	21.0	20.33
3c	7.5	8.0	8.5	8.0	-	-	-	-
Sulphanilamide	13.5	18.5	21.5	17.83	-	-	-	-
3d	13.5	18.5	21.5	17.83	12.5	17.5	21.5	17.17
Sulphacetamide	-	-	-	-	19.5	21.0	24.0	21.50
Avg. of concn.	10.58	12.33	14.42		12.17	13.58	15.25	
	S.Ed.	CD at 5%			S.Ed.	CD at 5%		
Compound	0.313	0.698			0.514	1.145		
Concentration	0.135	0.279			0.192	0.396		
Interaction	0.332	0.684			0.470	0.971		

S.Ed.-Standard error of difference; CD-Critical difference.

(d) at arbitrarily chosen concentration towards *B. subtilis*. This means that substitution of one of the hydrogen atom of the referred -NHCOCH₃ group resulted in the decrease of antimicrobial activity. From Table 4, it is further revealed that compound 3b and 3d show significantly higher zone of inhibition as compared to corresponding sulphonamide at these arbitrarily chosen concentrations towards *S. aureus* signifying the replacement of one of the hydrogen of the -N⁴H₂ group by (b) and (c), resulted in maximum inhibition.

Scheme 1. Reaction with primary amine.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography was used for monitoring the reaction and to check purity. UV spectra were studied on Shimadzu UV-160A, UV-visible spectrophotometer; IR spectra (KBr) were recorded as potassium bromide pellets on Shimadzu 820 IPC FTIR spectrometer and ^1H NMR spectra on Bruker DRX-300 FT NMR spectrometer and chemical shifts were expressed as (ppm) values against tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal reference. The chemical reagents used in the synthesis were purchased from E. Merck and Aldrich.

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds 3a-3d : Synthetic pathway¹³ is scanned in Scheme 1 and characterization data for the synthesized compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Synthesis of Mannich bases derived from sulphonamides (3a-3d) : For this purpose, Mannich bases were derived

from sulphonamides (**3a-3d**) in ethanolic solution of 0.01 mol of amide, 0.01 mol of sulfonamide and 2.5 mL of formaldehyde solution (37% v/v). The reaction mixture was then adjusted to the pH of 3.5 with hydrochloric acid and refluxed on water bath. The obtained product was recrystallized with dry distilled ethanol and DMF (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity : The disk diffusion method was used for assessing antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. Cultures of each bacterium, kept in Mullar Hinton Agar (Hi media) at 37 °C for 24 h and then examined. Most of the compounds were found to be effective against the tested microorganism by measuring the diameter of the growth inhibition zone according to Bauer *et al.*¹⁴.

These conclusions suggest that the four novel Mannich bases possess a very noticeable and prolonged antibacterial activity and further studies should be performed to

determine their value as antimicrobial agent. This work showed that Mannich bases are a potential source of compounds for inhibition of bacteria. We next focused our attention on antimicrobial analysis of Mannich bases of 2-chloro-4-nitrobenzamide towards various gram-positive and gram-negative pathogens.

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